

Conservation and management of the wolf population in Slovenia: legal aspects

Franci Avsec

Prof. Dr., University of Novo mesto (Slovenia)

Abstract

Aufgrund des großen Anteils der Wälder an der Gesamtfläche Sloweniens (58 %) und der Überwucherung landwirtschaftlicher Randflächen ist mit einer allmählichen Ausbreitung des Wolfs auch in Gebieten zu rechnen, in denen er derzeit nicht vorkommt. Die Koexistenz mit dem Wolf wird eine neue Herausforderung für die Anwohner, Viehzüchter und andere Akteure in diesen Gebieten darstellen. Dieser Beitrag beleuchtet die rechtliche Situation in Slowenien.

En raison de la part importante de forêts dans la superficie totale de la Slovénie (58 %) et de l'envahissement de terres agricoles adjacentes, on peut s'attendre à une expansion progressive du loup dans des zones où il n'est pas présent actuellement. La coexistence avec le loup constituera un nouveau défi pour les habitants, les éleveurs et les autres acteurs de ces régions. Cet article met en lumière la situation juridique en Slovénie.

1. Historical background and present state of the wolf population in Slovenia

The presence of the wolf on the territory of the today Slovenia in prehistoric and later periods until the second half of 19 century is evidenced by fossils and other sources. From the middle of the 19 century until the 1960s, the wolves were intensively hunted and almost to extirpated. They survived in the south-eastern part of Slovenia, mainly due to migration from the neighbouring Croatia.¹ In 1976, the Act Regulating the Protection, Breeding and Hunting of Wild Animals and the Management of Hunting Districts² laid down the hunting season for wolf and protected this species in the most sensitive period of giving birth to young.³

In 1976, the killing of wolves was permanently forbidden in the hunting ground Jelen-Snežnik on the own initiative of hunting organization. In 1990, the Hunting Association of Slovenia, on its own initiative, introduced all-year ban on hunting wolves on the entire territory of Slovenia.⁴

¹ M. Adamič, A. Kobler and M. Berce, Brief History of the Wolf-Human Interactions on the Today's Territory of Slovenia, Zbornik gozdarstva in lesarstva, vol. 57, 1998, p. 237-239.

² Zakon o varstvu, gojitvi in lovu divjadi ter o upravljanju lovišč, Uradni list Socialistične Republike Slovenije (Official Journal of Socialist Republic of Slovenia), no. 25/76, 29/86, Uradni list Republike Slovenije (Official Journal of Socialist Republic of Slovenia), no. 29/95, 89/99.

³ M. Jonozovič, Strokovno izhodišče za vzpostavlanje omrežja Natura 2000: Volk (Canis lupus L.) (Expert opinion for establishing the Natura 2000 network: Wolf /Canis lupus L./), Agencija RS za okolje, Ljubljana 2003, p. 20, available at: https://natura2000.gov.si/fileadmin/user_upload/Dokumenti/Strokovne_podlage/volk.pdf.

⁴ Ibidem, p. 20.

The scientific research shows that wolf subpopulations in south-central Slovenia and Gorski Kotar in Lika in Croatia are connected. Due to evident transboundary connections the conservation status of wolf in both countries depends on protection measures in Slovenia as well in Croatia.⁵ From a broader perspective, wolves in Slovenia represent the northwestern part of the Dinaric-Balkan wolf population, which extends to Greece in the south-east.⁶

Highways, large rivers, and railroads hinder wolves and other large carnivores in their movement, but are not permanently insurmountable obstacles for these species. After the first fenced highway in Slovenia had been built in 1972, a wolf pack the crossing of highway under its viaduct was tracked in 1993.⁷ In 1995, first wolves were noticed at the foothills of Jelovica Plateau in the Prealpine region.⁸

The most recent available report on wolf conservation status for the 2020/2021 season shows that there are approximately 120 wolves or 12 wolf packs (ten in the southern Slovenia and two in the Pokljuka and Jelovica areas) in Slovenia. Five wolf packs are assessed as vital, four have "emerging" status, one "disintegrating" status and two "unknown status".⁹ A special problem is hybridisation between a wolf and a domestic dog. One wolf-dog hybrid pack has been recently detected in the Italy-Austria-Slovenia three-border area.¹⁰

2. Legal acts on protection of wolves

The Slovenian Constitution¹¹ from 1991 determines everyone's obligation »to protect natural sites of special interest, rarities, and cultural monuments in accordance with the law«, while »the state and local communities are obliged promote the preservation of the natural and cultural heritage« (article 73). The Constitution also foresees protection of animals from cruelty which is regulated by law (article 72(4)).

In 1993, the Decree on the protection of endangered animal species¹² proclaimed certain species, including wolf, as outstanding natural features (article 1), prohibited killing, capture and disturbance of specimen of protected animal species (with very narrowly defined exceptions, article 3). The Decree

⁵ M. Adamič, A. Kobler and M. Berce, The Return of the Wolf (Canis Lupus) into its Historic Range in Slovenia – Is There Any Place Left and How to Reach It? Zbornik gozdarstva in lesarstva, 57 (1998), p. 246.

⁶ N. Ražen, Volkova raba prostora v pokrajini s prevladujočim človekovim vplivom - doktorska disertacija. (Wolf's use of space in a landscape with dominant human influence - doctoral dissertation), Univ. v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta, Ljubljana 2023, p. 105, available at: <https://repozitorij.uni-lj.si/Dokument.php?id=165783&lang=slv>.

⁷ M. Adamič, A. Kobler and M. Berce, op. cit., p. 242.

⁸ Ibidem, p. 245.

⁹ Spremljanje stanja ohranjenosti volkov v Sloveniji v sezoni 2020-2021, Končno poročilo, Ljubljana, oktober 2022 (Monitoring the conservation status of wolves in Slovenia in the 2020-2021 season, Final report, Ljubljana, October 2022), available at: https://volkovi.si/wp-content/uploads/Spremljanje_stanja_volka_2020_21_koncno_v2.pdf.

¹⁰ Government decisions taken at the Government committees meetings (7.11.2023), available at: <https://www.gov.si/en/news/2023-11-07-government-decisions-taken-at-the-government-committees-meetings/>.

¹¹ Ustava Republike Slovenije, Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 33/91-I, 42/97, 66/00, 24/03, 69/04, 68/06, 47/13, 47/13, 75/16, 92/21. Unofficial consolidated text no. 11 available at: <http://pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=USTA1>.

¹² Uredba o zavarovanju ogroženih živalskih vrst, Uradni list Republike Slovenije (Official Journal of the Republic of Slovenia), no. 57/93, 61/93 – popr., 69/00, 98/02 in 46/04.

explicitly forbade hunting of wolves, bears and lynxes. The ban on hunting could be exceptionally lifted by the minister's permission (article 4).

In 2002, the Slovenian National Assembly adopted the Nature Conservation Act which, inter alia, placed plants and animals under special state protection (article 12) and elaborated sustainable management of plant and animal species (article 16).

After Slovenia became Member of the European Union on 1st May 2004, the Habitat Directive¹³ which classifies wolves as animal species of Community interest in need of strict protection (Annex IV) was transposed in Slovenia by the Decree on protected wild animal species.¹⁴

Game management, which includes the planning, preservation, sustainable management and monitoring of the state of game, and methods of their implementation, is regulated by the Game and Hunting Act.¹⁵

The game and Hunting Act defines game as “species of wild mammals and birds that are hunted” and hunting as “activity of sustainable game management, in which legal persons that meet the prescribed conditions may be involved” (article 3(1)).

The Game and Hunting Act classifies wolf, bear and lynx as large carnivores. Because all three species are protected and may not be hunted, these species are not considered to be game. Thus, the Decree determining game animals and hunting seasons¹⁶ does not mention wolf, bear and lynx.

Nevertheless, the Game and Hunting Act contain some specific provisions on the large carnivores. In addition, this Act regulates management of game, including prey species of large carnivores, while the hunting organisations, founded in accordance with this Act, participate in the implementation of certain measures related to sustainable management of the wolf. Therefore, a brief survey of relevant provisions may be useful to get a larger picture of the relevant normative framework.

The game management is based on the game management programme, game management plans and development plans for nature protection, development of forests, agriculture and other activities. The body responsible for planning and monitoring the state of game is the Forest Service of Slovenia.

For the purpose of game management, the territory of the Republic of Slovenia is divided into hunting management regions the boundaries of which are determined by the government on the proposal of minister, responsible for game and hunting, in collaboration with the minister, responsible for nature protection.

¹³ Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora, OJ L 206, 22.7.1992, p. 7.

¹⁴ Uredba o zavarovanih prosto živečih živalskih vrstah, Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 46/04, 109/04, 84/05, 115/07, 32/08, 96/08, 36/09, 102/11, 15/14, 64/16 in 62/19. Unofficial consolidated text no. 10 available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=URED2386>.

¹⁵ Zakon o divjadi in lovstvu, Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 16/04, 120/06 – odl. US, 17/08, 46/14 – ZON-C, 31/18, 65/20, 97/20, 44/22, 158/22. Unofficial consolidated text no. 7 available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO3780>.

¹⁶ Uredba o določitvi divjadi in lovnih dob (Decree determining game animals and hunting seasons), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 101/04, 81/14. Unofficial consolidated text no. 1 available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=URED3478>.

Game management regions are, for the implementation of planned measures, divided into 111 hunting districts and 10 special purpose hunting districts.¹⁷

A hunting district is a specifically integral area of land and water comprising not be less than 2,000 ha of hunting area and which enables (1) rational and harmonised division and the implementation of planned measures and tasks of the game management, (2) ensuring funds for compensation of damage caused by game to land owners and (3) effective monitoring and control of game management (article 8 of the Game and Hunting Act).

The Government of the Republic of Slovenia awards concessions to hunting societies (established in the legal form of association) for sustainable game management in hunting districts. Hunting societies must manage hunting grounds in a sustainable manner. Concessions are awarded for a specified period which may not be shorter than 20 years (articles 24 and 25 of the Game and Hunting Act).

The concessionaire must pay annually the concession fee which is calculated as certain percent (but not less than 10%) of the five-year average of annual revenue from the hunting district management. One half of the concession fee is allocated to State budget, while another half is the revenue of municipalities in which the hunting district is located proportionally with the size of this area in individual municipality. The concessionaire may not give a hunting district for lease or sub-lease, but may delegate to a third person the performance of individual measures and tasks (article 29 of the Game and Hunting Act).

The game management is based on the game management programme, adopted at the state level, long-term game management plans and annual plans of hunting management regions as well as annual plans of hunting districts and hunting districts with special purpose, and other plans relating to forestry, agriculture, nature conservation and environment (articles 4 and 12-14 of the Game and Hunting Act).

The Game and Hunting Act contains no provision on the ownership of the game. According to previous legal regime, the game was social ownership. The captured, or killed game and game trophies belonged to the hunting organization managing the hunting ground while this organisation was authorized to lay down the manner in which the trophy became the property of an individual.¹⁸

The first Environmental Protection Act from 1993¹⁹ explicitly established the state ownership of the wild plant and animal species (article 111). A similar provision on state ownership of the game could also be found in the second Environmental Protection Act from 2004 (article 163(2)).²⁰ Such provision

¹⁷ M. Bedrač et al., Poročilo o stanju kmetijstva, živilstva, gozdarstva in ribištva 2022 (Report on the state of agriculture, food, forestry and fisheries 2022), p. 194.

¹⁸ Zakon o varstvu, gojitvi in lovu divjadi ter o upravljanju lovišč (Act Regulating the Protection, Breeding and Hunting of Wild Animals and the Management of Hunting Ground), Uradni list Socialistic Republic of Slovenia, no. 25/76, 29/86, Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 29/95, 89/99, article 3 and 7.

¹⁹ Zakon o varstvu okolja - ZVO, (Environmental Protection Act), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 32/93, 1/96, 56/99, 22/00, 67/02.

²⁰ Zakon o varstvu okolja - ZVO-1 (Environmental protection Act), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 41/04, 17/06, 20/06, 49/06, 66/06, 33/07, 57/08, 70/08, 108/09, 108/09, 48/12, 57/12, 92/13, 56/15, 102/15, 30/16, 61/17, 21/18, 84/18, 158/20. The unofficial consolidated text no. 20 available at: <http://pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO1545>.

was foreseen also by the governmental Proposal for the third Environmental Protection Act²¹, but was not taken over into the final text of the Environmental Protection Act from 2022²² currently in force.

The Forest Service prepares the technical basis for the game management programme and plans, collects, analyses and processes data on the state of game populations. It also implementing measures for ensuring the coexistence of protected species of large carnivores with humans, in accordance with adopted strategies and action plans.

3. The programmes and action plans on conservation and sustainable management of wolves

The National Environment Protection Programme with programmes of measures until 2030²³ states that the condition of the species whose habitat is the agricultural landscape and the habitat types that are linked to this habitat is deteriorating. The agricultural use of these areas is a precondition for ensuring habitat and habitat types for these species. On the other side, agricultural intensification is a major threat to the favorable condition of European important species and habitat types. The condition of the forests is generally assessed as “good, including some typical species that live there (eg. wolf, bear)” (Section 5.1), the only exceptions are special forest habitats and habitat types (eg. in lowland flood forests). Pressures and threats for European important species and habitat types in Slovenia originate from construction, urbanization, industrialization, production of energy, climate change and the spread of invasive species.

The Strategy for Conservation and Sustainable Management of Wolf (*Canis lupus*) in Slovenia²⁴ was adopted in 2009. Its aim is to ensure a favorable state of conservation in Slovenia and thus contribute to viability Dinaric-Balkan populations because the coexistence of a man with a wolf is not feasible

²¹ Predlog Zakon o varstvu okolja - ZVO-2 (Proposal for Environmental Protection Act), EVA 2020-2550-0094, Prva obravnava (First Reading), available at: <https://tinyurl.com/h6k935e4>.

²² Zakon o varstvu okolja (ZVO-2), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 44/22, 18/23, 78/23. The Legislative and Legal Service of the of the National Assembly criticized the proposed provision on state ownership of the game from three aspects: (1) such provision of the Environmental protection Act would mean a departure from the regulation of legal matter according to substantive criteria and would be inconsistent with (2) the definition of things and (3) the special status of animals under the Law of Property Code. Namely, this Code defines thing as an “independent external object that can be controlled by a person, according to the service” (art. 15(1)) and the question arises how the State as the owner would control the game, since wild game can cross state borders and there is no administrative control over game (for example, a register). On the other hand, the provision of the Law of Property Code defining animals as “sentient living beings” (article 15a), not things, speaks against the state's ownership of wild game (Zakonodajna služba, Mnenje o predlogu zakona o varstvu okolja (ZVO-2), druga obravnava, /Legislative and Legal Service, Opinion on Proposal of Environmental Protection Act (ZVO-2), second reading/, EPA 2317-VIII, available at: <https://tinyurl.com/yc86ns3k>).

²³ Resolucija o Nacionalnem programu varstva okolja za obdobje 2020–2030 (National Environment Protection Programme with programmes of measures until 2030), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 31/20, 44/22, available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ODLO1985>.

²⁴ Strategija ohranjanja volka (*Canis lupus*) v Sloveniji in trajnostnega upravljanja z njim (The Strategy for Conservation and Sustainable Management of Wolf /*Canis lupus*/ in Slovenia), 2009, available at: https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MNVP/Dokumenti/Narava/Velike-zveri/strategija_ohranjanja_volka.pdf.

without adequate measures. The strategy contains main guidelines for formation of an appropriate human-wolf relationship which is dynamic and permanent task.

The Strategy consists of (1) introduction, (2) legal acts regulatuing or having impact on wolf protection of wolf in Slovenia, (3) relationship between man and wolf in Slovenia, (4) analysis of endangerment and existing conservation measures, (5) goals of conservation and sustainable management of wolf population in Slovenia, (6) guidelines for achieving goals, (7) provision of financial funds, (9) adoption and implementing of strategy and action plans and (10) references.

The introduction to the Strategy explains the strategy goals, biological characteristics of wolf, historical dispersal of the wolf species in the Slovenian territory and the present wolf population status in Slovenia.

The second section about legal acts regulating or affecting wolf protection in Slovenia enumerates and briefly summarizes international treaties as well internal laws and executive regulations which regulate wolf conservation.

The third section of the Strategy notes the key impact of man on wolf population and its numerousness.

Stating that the wolf, compared to the brown bear, is not physically dangerous to humans (except in exceptional cases), the Strategy enumerates following causes of conflicts between wolves and humans:

- man perceives the wolf as a competitor in hunting deer and roe deer,
- the wolf can be in the area of its permanent and occasional presence in individual cases the limiting factor of domestic animal husbandry, especially of small animals,
- a historically determined fear of the wolf.²⁵

With regard to the spatial framework for conservation of wolf in Slovenia, the Strategy emphasizes that management of large carnivore populations, especially wolves, can only be successfully if simultaneously enforced in large areas. Since wolves are not typical habitat specialists, they are not necessarily bound only to forested areas and are able to adapt well to areas where there are enough prey species and they are not persecuted by humans. According to the Strategy, decrees on ecologically important areas²⁶ and on special protection areas (areas Natura 2000)²⁷ precisely define spatial frameworks in Slovenia in which wolf habitats must be conserved and sustainably managed, while in other parts of the wolf dispersal area favorable population state must be maintained. The Strategy attaches great importance to migration corridors. concluding that only the entire Dinaric-Balkan population area stretching from Greece and Albania across Montenegro, Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina,

²⁵ Ibidem, p. 14.

²⁶ Uredba o ekološko pomembnih območjih (Decree on ecologically important areas), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 48/04, 33/13, 99/13 in 47/18, available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=URED629>.

²⁷ Uredba o posebnih varstvenih območjih (območjih Natura 2000) (Decree on special protection areas (Natura 2000 areas)), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 49/04, 110/04, 59/07, 43/08, 8/12, 33/13, 35/13, 39/13, 3/14, 21/16, 47/18, available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=URED283>.

Serbia and Croatia to the southern half of Slovenia, large enough and suitable for preservation viable wolf populations in South-Eastern Europe.

The Strategy pursues good conservation status of the wolf. Such goal may be attained by monitoring of the wolf population, populations of prey and competing species, dynamics and density of the wolf population. The relationship between man and wolf may be improved by education and information as well as inclusion of local residents. Interventions in the wolf population must be based on objective findings.

Assessing the preservation and biological diversity of Slovenian forests as good, the Strategy emphasizes the importance of forest management planning in order to ensure preservation of habitats suitable for a wolf. Protection of these habitats must be taken into account when planning larger transport infrastructure facilities. In such cases it is necessary to determine the location of main corridors which allow the wolf to pass smoothly from one area to another. On the other hand, the game management planning must take into account the impact of large carnivores and of a man on prey species.

The agricultural sector may contribute to achievement of strategy goals by corresponding measures of agricultural policy which promote and subsidize suitable methods of protection of farm animals on pastures (electric fences and nets, protection by shepherds, sheepdogs and herding dogs, closing the herd at night). Efficient compensation system of compensation for damage caused by large carnivores may prevent conflicts with breeders.

For better involvement of stakeholders (local residents, livestock farmers, hunters, non-governmental organisations etc.) and other public in the wolf conservation the Strategy recommends education and information about wolves and their role in ecosystem. These activities presuppose further scientific and research work as well as cross border cooperation. In recent years several projects in the area of wolf conservation have been launched (SloWolf, 2010-2014²⁸, Carnivora Dinarica, 2018-2021²⁹; LIFE WolfAlps EU, 2019-2024³⁰).

4. Compensation for damage caused by wolf and other specimens of protected animal species

According to the general principle of the Slovenian Nature Conservation Act, the State is not liable for damage caused by plants or animals (article 91). However, the liability of State or hunting organisation for damage caused by game, is regulated by the Game and Hunting Act, while the Nature Conservation Act lays down conditions under which the State is liable for damage caused by animals of protected species.

According to the Nature Conservation Act, persons whose property might be damaged by animals of the protected species are obliged to act with due care and attention and must take, at their expense, all the necessary measures to protect their property from damage. If the damage cannot be prevented

²⁸ Projekt SloWolf: Povzetek rezultatov (Project SloWolf: Summary of Results), available at: https://www.volkovi.si/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/slowolf_layman-report_slo_04.pdf.

²⁹ Project Carnivora Dinarica, available at: <https://www.dinapivka.si/en/project/project-carnivora-dinarica/>.

³⁰ Life WolfAlps: General information, available at: <https://www.lifewolfalps.eu/en/about-the-project/>.

in such manner, the person may request that the Ministry, responsible for nature conservation, implements appropriate measures to prevent further damage. In such a case, the requesting person and the Ministry agree on the types of measures and the manner of providing funds for the implementation of the measures. Such measures may be deterrence, building of enclosures, taking individual specimens from the wild and reducing the populations of protected animal species.

The Act authorized minister to determine appropriate manner of protection of property and the types of measures for the prevention of damage with regard to individual animal species.

According to the Rules on the appropriate manner of protecting property and the types of measures for preventing further damage to property³¹ issued by the Minister of environment and space, deterrence and fencing are suitable methods of property protection. The deterrence may not consist of prohibited disturbance of specimen of protected species. In individual cases, other measures may also be considered to be appropriate if determined in the record of the occurrence of the damage (article 4 of the Rules).

In order to prevent *further* damage to protected animal species, deterrence and fencing with more demanding technical implementation must be applied. If the implementation of these measures does not prevent occurrence of further damage, the injured party may submit a reasoned proposal for culling or trapping of individual specimen of protected animal species in accordance with the regulations on nature conservation (article 5 of the Rules).

According to Annex I to the Rules, a suitable way to protect property from wolves is electric fence with more than one wire, adapted to the type of animal being protected and the type of animal before which the aforementioned animal is protected. To prevent further damage to property caused by the wolf, the Annex II to the Rules specifies as suitable measures fencing (electric fence with 5-7 wires or farm netting with reinforcement) and deterrence (shepherd dog).

In order to prevent damage on farm animals on pastures caused by large carnivores, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food recommends electric fences (at least 160 cm high), massive fences and stables, protection by a shepherd or shepherd dogs.³² The rural development measures in the period 2013-2022 included also subsidies for herd protection by high movable protective electric grids, by the presence of the shepherd and by shepherd dogs.³³

³¹ Pravilnik o primernih načinih varovanja premoženja in vrstah ukrepov za preprečitev nadaljnje škode na premoženju, Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 74/05, available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=PRAV6741>.

³² T. Berce and R. Černe, Reja domačih živali in sobivanje z zvermi – Varovanje drobnice pred velikimi zvermi, Ministrstvo za kmetijstvo, gozdarstvo in prehrano, Ljubljana 2016.

³³ Uredba o ukrepih kmetijsko-okoljska-podnebna plačila, ekološko kmetovanje in plačila območjem z naravnimi ali drugimi posebnimi omejitvami iz Programa razvoja podeželja Republike Slovenije za obdobje 2014–2020 (Decree on the measures of agri-environment-climate payments, organic farming, and payments to areas facing natural or other specific constraints, laid down in the Rural Development Programme of the Republic of Slovenia 2014–2020), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 16/16, 51/16, 84/16, 15/17, 63/17, 68/17, 5/18, 65/18, 81/18, 10/19, 76/19, 7/20, 61/20, 78/20, 26/21, 197/21, 20/22, 157/22, 34/23, articles 98-102. The unofficial consolidated text no. 18 available at: <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=URED7211>.

The Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment co-finances the implementation of measures (equipment for protection with high electric grids or protection with a multi-wire electric fence) to prevent further damage caused by large carnivores.³⁴

The state budget allocates certain funds exclusively to forest owners for the maintenance of the living environment of wild animals. If the forest owners are not interested in doing the work themselves, they can assign the work and the right to receive the subsidy to the contractor (hunting societies).³⁵

The person who, in spite of having taken all preventive measures suffers damage inflicted by protected species, must within three days of noticing the damage, report it in writing to the regional unit of the Slovenian Forest Service, where the damage occurred, and insure the place where the damage occurred.

The authorized officer employed at the Slovenian Forest Service inspects the scene of the incident within two days of reporting the damage and records his findings in the Record Book.

Table 1: Value of damage caused by individual animal species in the period 2012-2021

Species / Year	Bear	Wolf	Lynx	Beaver	Otter
2012	248.085	192.710	547	337	2.504
2013	162.633	89.934	0	637	4.778
2014	258.845	135.702	0	1.669	1.075
2015	159.807	92.281	169	250	n. a.
2016	162.202	65.155	25	2.922	13.600
2017	219.003	150.002	1.058	3.004	835
2018	75.411	125.193	169	7.114	710

³⁴ The electrical grid must be at least 160 cm high, the minimum perimeter of the pen must be 300 meters (valid for the protection of grazing animals) and the maximum perimeter of the corral is 500 meters (for the protection of grazing animals). The fence must consist of at least 6 lines of galvanized wire and must be at least 150 cm high, thickness of galvanized wire must be at least 1.5 mm etc. The injured party who suffered damage by large carnivores and who, as a good owner, did everything necessary to protect his property from damage, fills out the application form describing the damage and indicating the equipment for co-financing. The Ministry of Natural Resources and Space verifies the entitlement of the injured party to co-financing and, prepares, if the conditions are met, a tripartite agreement on the co-financing of the implementation of measures to prevent further damage, between the injured party, the Forestry Service of Slovenia (ZGS) and the Ministry of Natural Resources and Space. For details, see *Odškodnina za škodo na premoženju zaradi zavarovane vrste živali (rjavi medved, volk, in drugi)* (Compensation for damage to property caused by an insured animal species /brown bear, wolf, and others/), available at: <https://www.gov.si/zbirke/storitve/odskodnina-za-skodo-na-premozenju-zaradi-zavarovane-vrste-zivali-rjavi-medved-volk/>.

³⁵ M. Bedrač et al., op. cit., p. 196.

2019	163.848	248.496	182	3.699	140.315
2020	112.950	142.899	0	5.179	77
2021	204.595	83.067	240	11.679	356

Source: Poročila o škodah in baza škod, available at: <https://www.varna-pasa.si/skodni-primeri/porocila-o-skodah-in-baza-skod/>

After inspection of the site of the damage event, the authorized person and the injured party may draw up a proposal for an agreement on the amount of compensation up to the amount specified in the Price List for assessing damage caused by animals of insured species³⁶ or to the amount specified in the Compendium of market purchase prices of agricultural products, published on the website of the ministry, responsible for agriculture.

The injured party who does not agree with the determination of compensation based on the Price list or the Compendium, may submit a compensation claim with an application to the Ministry of Natural Resources and Space.

After having checked the record and the proposed agreement or the injured party's claim, the Ministry decides on the amount and payment of compensation.

The injured party who does not agree with the Ministry's decision may request, by means of a lawsuit, that compensation be decided upon by the competent court. The lawsuit must be filed no later than three years from the day on which the damage occurred (article 93 of the Nature Conservation Act).

5. Selective and limited removal of certain animals

The Decree on protected wild animal species allows that the ministry responsible for nature conservation to permit certain actions which depart from prohibition of killing, removal from nature, trapping, disturbing, poisoning or injury of animals of the animal species. Such permission may be issued only if two general requirements, namely, that (1) there is no other satisfactory option and (2) these actions do not harm the preservation of the favourable state of the population are cumulatively met and the action derogating from the prohibition is justified due to:

- 1) ensuring the benefits of the protection of animal and plant species and the preservation of habitat types,
- 2) prevention of serious damage, especially to crops, livestock, forests, fishing grounds and water and other property (whereby the reason for preventing serious damage to other property does not apply to birds, and the reason for serious damage to forests does not apply to African-Eurasian waterfowl from Annex 2 of the Agreement on the Conservation of African-Eurasian Migratory Waterbirds),

³⁶ Cenik za ocenjevanje škode, ki jo povzročijo živali zavarovanih vrst (Price list for assessment of damage caused by animals of insured species), available at: <https://www.gov.si/zbirke/storitve/odskodnina-za-skodo-na-premozenju-zaradi-zavarovane-vrste-zivali-rjavi-medved-volk/>.

- 3) ensuring the health and safety of people, including air safety, or due to other urgent reasons of overriding public benefit, which may also be social or economic, and due to beneficial consequences of essential importance for the environment (whereby other urgent reasons of overriding public benefit, which can also be social or economic, are not applicable to birds),
- 4) immigration or repopulation of animals, including breeding, for the purposes of immigration or repopulation,
- 5) selective and limited trapping, fitting with tags and transmitters or intervention that may cause damage, or taking animals for research purposes,
- 6) selective and limited trapping or removal of animals for educational purposes,
- 7) selective and limited removal of certain animals from nature under strictly controlled conditions and in limited numbers.

The Administrative Court of the Republic of Slovenia took the view that “the objectives of the Habitats Directive were transposed into the Slovenian legal order in such a way that article 7 of the Decree on protected wild animal species summarizes the basic conditions set out in article 16 of the Habitats Directive.”³⁷

The Administrative Court argued that reason from the seventh (last) indent of Article 7(1) of the Slovenian Decree reasonably contains a further condition, which is otherwise not explicitly stated in the previously mentioned normative texts: the existence of a problem or situation, connected with the presence of wolf as protected species, for the solution of which the removal of specimens of a protected species from the wild must be allowed exceptionally. Otherwise, the Court explained, this reason would remain meaningless or empty, since it would allow "removal for the sake of removal" and the second of the aforementioned conditions, that "there is no other satisfactory option", would also remain completely meaningless in such a case. The Guidelines of the European Commission lead to the same conclusion.³⁸

In the same case the ministry which issued a permission for removal of limited number of wolves justified the measure referring to a survey of public opinion and other sources, according to which the attitude of the general public and hunters towards large carnivores, specifically wolves, was predominantly positive, while livestock farmers expressed great dissatisfaction. The court was the opinion that the public attitude towards wolves might not be equated with the social acceptability of the concerned animal species, especially since the ministry as defendant stated that the general public's attitude towards large carnivores was positive. The Court added that the removal of a limited number of animals may not decisively contribute to change of the public opinion.³⁹

According to article 7a of the Decree on protected wild animal species, the Government of the Republic of Slovenia may, in the case referred to in the seventh indent of the article 7(1), take measure to remove animals from the wild (except birds) by ordinance. If a strategy, action plan or other program

³⁷ Upravno sodišče Republike Slovenije, Sodba (Judgment) no. I U 102/2018-17 from 6 September 2018, available at: <https://tinyurl.com/4pa8uz28>.

³⁸ Ibidem.

³⁹ Ibidem.

document is adopted to ensure a favorable state of animal species, the Government's ordinance must also take into account the guidelines from these documents. The ordinance may determine other conditions for the removal of animals from the wild, in particular:

- the method of determining the scope of taking animals from the wild,
- a more detailed method of taking animals from the wild and
- monitoring the removal and keeping records of animals taken from the wild.

Regardless whether the limited and selective removal of specimen of protected animal species is decided by the minister or by the government, the measure must be based on the expert opinion of organization responsible for nature conservation - the Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Nature Conservation. However, for limited and selective removal of large carnivores, the expert opinion is prepared by the Slovenian Forest Service, to which the written position of the organization responsible for nature conservation must be attached.

In April 2019, the Administrative Court issued the judgement (no. I U 2541/2018⁴⁰) abolished the Annex to the governmental Ordinance on the measure of removal of individuals of the brown bear species (*Ursus arctos*) from the wild for the period until 30 September 2019⁴¹ and returned the matter in this part to the Government for a new procedure. Instead of adopting a new ordinance that would replace the former Ordinance, the Government prepared a proposal for Act Regulating the Intervention Culling of Specimens of Brown Bear (*Ursus arctos*) and Common Wolf (*Canis lupus*) from the Wild which was adopted by the National Assembly under an urgent procedure.⁴²

Two non-governmental organizations challenged the Act on the interventional removal of specimens of the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) and wolf (*Canis lupus*) species from nature before the Constitutional Court.

The government stated that the challenged Act was prepared with the aim of preventing difficult-to-repair consequences for the functioning of the state, which could arise from the judicial suspension of the enforcement of already adopted ordinance on measures to remove bears and wolves from the wild.

The Constitutional Court found out that the challenged Act essentially determined the exact number of culled bears and wolves in terms of time, territory, conditions and restrictions that hunting associations must observe when carrying out such culling. Therefore, the challenged Act had the nature of an individual legal act and was inconsistent with the constitutional principle of the separation of powers. The Constitutional Court abrogated the challenged Act.⁴³

⁴⁰ Upravno sodišče RS, Sodba no. I U 2541/2018-26 from 10 4. 2019, available at: <https://tinyurl.com/3cr2kuj5>.

⁴¹ Odlok o ukrepu odvzema osebkov vrste rjavega medveda (*Ursus arctos*) iz narave za obdobje do 30. septembra 2019 (Ordinance on culling specimens of brown bear /*Ursus arctos*/ from the wild for the period until 30 September 2019), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 74/18, available at: <https://tinyurl.com/44x6hs6b>.

⁴² Zakon o interventnem odvzemu osebkov vrst rjavega medveda (*Ursus arctos*) in volka (*Canis lupus*) iz narave – ZIOMVN (), Uradni list Republike Slovenije, no. 43/19, available at: <https://tinyurl.com/3svrvy9t>.

⁴³ Odločba (Decision) no. U-I-194/19-24 from 9. 4. 2020, available at: <https://www.us-rs.si/odlocitev/?q=odvzemu+volkov&order=desc&id=114238>.

The decisions on limited and selective removal of animals of protected species must take into account also ascertained losses of such animals (traffic accidents etc.).

Table 2: Statistical data on culling and ascertained losses large carnivores in Slovenia from 2012-2022

Species/ Year	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Wolf	14	3	12	7	2	8	11	20	14	6	9
Bear	132	63	143	113	47	122	153	183	99	148	234
Lynx	2	0	1	0	2	0	0	2	1	2	1

Source: M. Bedrač et al., Poročilo o stanju kmetijstva, živilstva, gozdarstva in ribištva 2022 (Report on the state of agriculture, food, forestry and fisheries 2022), Ljubljana, junij 2023, p. 195.

6. Conclusion

Due to the large proportion of forests in the total surface of Slovenia (58 %) and the overgrowing of marginal agricultural land, gradually increasing dispersal of the wolf can also be expected in areas where it is not present now. The co-existence with the wolf will represent new challenge for local residents, livestock farmers and other stakeholders in these areas. The experts warn that in Alpine mountains where wolves are now noticed more often than before, the protective measures to prevent the damage on property caused by large carnivores are more difficult to implement than in Dinaric mountains and that the knowledge on such protection practically does not exist among residents of the Alpine regions.⁴⁴

Replying to two questions the National Council Commissions with regard to conservation of wolf population in Slovenia in November 2023, the Slovenian government stressed that the wolf population in Slovenia is divided between the Dinarides and the Alps biogeographical regions. The government is of the opinion that Slovenia cannot currently support a downgrading of the wolf conservation status, because the the conservation status of the species in the two biogeographical regions is not uniform or favourable in all countries of each biogeographical region. The government also expressed its intent to adopt a new wolf management strategy in 2024.⁴⁵

Some experts think that the wolf and bear populations in Slovenia have been strengthening »(too) quickly« in recent years . According to these views, the greatest danger for the bear and wolf are polarized standpoints in the society ranging from proponents of absolute protection of every single specimen to proponents of (at least local) extinction of carnivores. The updating of the European

⁴⁴ M. Bartol and M. Stergar, Upravljanje velikih zveri v Sloveniji (Management of large carnivores in Slovenia), Gozdarski vestnik, 77(2019), p. 343.

⁴⁵ Government decisions taken at the Government committees meetings, 7. 11. 2023, available at: <https://www.gov.si/en/news/2023-11-07-government-decisions-taken-at-the-government-committees-meetings/>.

environmental legislation would, according to them, facilitate the search for solutions that would be acceptable for the widest possible range of stakeholders.⁴⁶

The current compensation system is criticized for two drawbacks. The first one is the requirement that breeders are entitled funds for protective measures only after the damage caused by protected animal species has already occurred. The second one is the manner of fixing the compensation which is in many cases too low to recover the entire damage caused by the protected species.

⁴⁶ M. Bartol and M. Stergar, *op. cit.*, p. 344.